

INDICATORS OF ENVIRONMENTAL CULTURE OF STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the research developed and conducted by the authors in the Almalyk branch of TSTU, which are of interest from the point of view of understanding the environmental culture of young people in modern society.

Introduction. An increase in anthropogenic pressure on the natural environment has caused the globalization of environmental problems [10]. Experts note with alarm the growth of pollution of atmospheric air, fresh water, the World Ocean, the soil layer, deforestation, erosion and salinization of soils, a decrease in their fertility, desertification, a rise in the level of the World Ocean, a decrease in biodiversity and global climate warming. The growth rate of surface temperature today has reached the highest values in the last 600 thousand years, which is explained by the rapid increase in the concentration of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases [3, p. 31].

The environmental degradation that has taken place is called a social problem, because it is largely due to human economic activity and has serious consequences for him. It is no coincidence that modern society is called the risk

society [1], and attention is focused on the risks of an anthropogenic nature [2].

Today, more and more countries, including Uzbekistan, are joining the implementation of the concept of "Sustainable Development" [9], according to which humanity must coordinate its activities with the laws of nature, change consumer attitudes towards nature. An important condition for the transition of modern society to "sustainable development" is the formation of an ecological culture in a person. In the context of the aggravation of the ecological situation, the determination of the possibilities for solving the environmental problem, which would be based on the development of the interaction of nature, society and culture, the processes of formation of ecological culture and the corresponding forms of human life, acquires particular relevance. The tension of the environmental situation actualizes the study of the dynamics of environmental consciousness,

environmental attitudes and environmental behavior of the population and its individual socio-demographic groups.

The ecological culture of modern Uzbek society is dominated by utilitarian individualistic attitudes. In this regard, there is a need to form a new human culture, in the way of life and behavior of which a new attitude to the environment is an integral feature. Human life and its preservation, reproduction of biological, social, cultural life, life of the biosphere and society are the criteria for environmental friendliness. In this context, it is relevant to analyze the content of ecological culture, taking into account specific features [4], specifying universal human values in relation to the perception of nature and culture as a certain unity. It is also important to study ecological culture at the sociological level to identify the qualitative characteristics and quantitative parameters of its various elements and their relationship. [5, p.54].

Therefore, studies conducted among young people are especially interesting, as they allow predicting the development of the ecological culture of society in the near future.

Literature review. Modern studies of ecological culture are based on a fundamental scientific base created by representatives of various sciences. Separate theoretical provisions explaining the processes of interaction between society and nature found justification in the "sociologism" of E. Durkheim; the theory of class struggle by K. Marx; Protestant ethics of M. Weber and other works of representatives of classical sociology.

A significant number of studies are devoted to the study of the problems of the

formation of ecological culture from general scientific positions, from the standpoint of systemic, synergistic, cultural approaches. Of particular interest are "multi-approach" work or work carried out at the junction of several directions. It is impossible not to note the attention to the problems of ecological culture on the part of environmental sociology A.V. Mozgovoy, M.A. I.A. Khaliy, O.N. Yanitsky. Valuable analytical and empirical data are given in the works of O.N. Yanitsky, V.A. Yadov, and other scientists.

It should be noted that the diversity of goals and objectives, the proposed methods and methods for the formation of ecological culture makes it difficult to obtain a holistic view of the structure of such activities.

Materials and methods. Some provisions of cultural studies, cultural anthropology and sociology of culture, which are reflected in the works of foreign and domestic researchers, acted as the methodological foundations of the study. In particular, of interest is the idea formed by M. Mead [6] and J. Murdoch [7] about "cultural patterns" that play the role of adaptation mechanisms that help individuals solve the problems of social existence and learning, in the process of which common patterns turn into individual skills.

In the analysis of ecological culture, synergistic institutional, factorial approaches were used. These approaches do not contradict each other, but complement each other due to the interdisciplinary perspective of considering the problem of "man-society-nature".

The empirical basis of the study was the following materials: a) legal documents of

the Republic of Uzbekistan on environmental issues and the formation of ecological culture; b) publications in the field of environmental protection, materials on environmental awareness and environmental education of the population, analytical documents on the directions and principles of the formation of their environmental culture; c) the results of content analysis of materials in scientific, journalistic and popular publications on the formation of the ecological culture of youth; d) the results of a sociological study among students of various universities on their assessment of the need for environmental education and its state, in the areas of formation of their environmental culture; e) the results of a sociological survey of students conducted in the Almalyk branch of TSTU to assess the level of their general and environmental culture.

Research results. The purpose of our research was to study the understanding of environmental culture by young people in modern society on the example of students of the Almalyk branch of TSTU. The survey was conducted among 3rd year students of the specialties "Technology of Mechanical Engineering", "Technology of Mechanical Engineering, Automation and Equipment", "Electrical Engineering and Electromechanics", "Chemical Technology". A total of 144 people took part in the survey. We developed a questionnaire, which consisted of 22 questions. As the survey showed, the majority of students, regardless of their professional orientation, do not have an accurate idea of what ecology studies as a science, and do not know the content of the concept of "human ecological culture". So, on the first question, 38% gave an absolutely correct answer,

and 58% gave an answer close in meaning. To the question "What is an ecological culture?" 24% of students mentioned the correct answer, the rest made an erroneous choice in favor of answers on general ecology. Thus, students find it difficult to single out the specifics of a certain area of environmental knowledge associated with the ecological culture of a person. Regarding the characteristics of the environmental situation in the city of Almalyk, the vast majority of respondents (81%) identified it as bad. The main reasons for the poor environmental situation in the city were the following: dirty air (45%) fresh water pollution - (21%); due to emissions of processed products from factories and plants that do not have a high-quality waste treatment and filtration system; air pollution (36%), dust (2%) and noise (5%); a lot of garbage (33%); dirty in the yards (16%); few park areas and green spaces (10%); many smokers (1%). As sources that help students in assessing the ecological state of the urban environment, in order of decreasing frequency of their mention, personal experience (34%), the media (29%), and other sources (16%) were noted.

Attention to environmental issues in the country in recent years was also noted as a factor in assessing the ecology in the city (32%). Describing the measure and degree of responsibility for the environmental situation in the city, it can be noted that 15% of the subjects entrust these powers to the Government, 21% to the city khokim, and the majority (65%) believe that the population in general and every resident of the city in particular must take care of the environment. Of these, 11 people (9%) out of 144 respondents believe that the

responsibility lies with the Government, the city khokim and the population combined. Investigating the dependence of the poor environmental situation in the city on the well-being of the population, 51% of the respondents answered that it most likely has a negative effect, 32% indicated that this influence is strong, according to 10% there is no influence, and 7% found it difficult to answer. To resolve the environmental situation in the city for the better, the most frequently proposed measures were the installation of modern efficient treatment plants and filters at functioning enterprises (12%), their removal outside the city (3%); landscaping of the city (12%); switching to electric vehicles (11%), reducing the number of cars or limiting their operation (6%); cleaning (9%) and processing (10%) of garbage; high-quality street cleaning (10%); introduction of fines and sanctions for non-compliance with environmental standards and requirements (10%); improvement of ecological culture and education among the population (10%). Among the less frequently mentioned answers were such as carrying out environmental campaigns (7%), an increase in the number of trash cans (3%) and janitors (3%), more social advertising (3%) and funds for cleaning the city (2%), in including not littering yourself (5%), first of all. A number of questions in the questionnaire concerned the socio-psychological orientation of human life as a factor in its harmonious development. Among the respondents, it was possible to reveal that 25% of students are focused only on their studies, 17% combine study and work, and the remaining 58% study and would like to work.

Quite interesting were the students' answers regarding life values and priorities, which directly affected the results of the research. Regardless of the specialty, family values are in the first place, health is in the second, career growth and hobbies are in the penultimate and last. In the specialty "Chemical Technology", where the main contingent is girls, the third place was given to the feeling of love, and in other specialties with a predominance of boys, this place was taken by friendship. Despite the above answers, the majority of students (83%) admit that in the pursuit of material values a person is able to lose moral qualities, lose health, love, and friends. This shows that there is a problem of hidden priorities that can show up under certain circumstances.

The problem of lonely people in cities, raised in one of the questions, found a positive response from a significant number of young people (69%), as other answers, 17% consider this problem exaggerated, and 14% did not hear anything about it. As possible causes of loneliness, more often than others were called isolation (19%), difficult character (14%), high employment (13%), comfortable being alone (12%), inability to communicate (11%) and lack of mutual understanding with others (6%), self-doubt (7%). Rare answers were insufficient attention from relatives and difficulties in the family, upbringing and behavior of a person, his bad habits, laziness, selfishness, passion for computer games and the Internet.

Discussion and conclusions. Thus, the study showed that the problems associated with the environmental aspects of human life in a modern city do exist. The younger generation sees a way out of this situation

in the joint efforts of the government and the head of the city, in an understanding attitude towards the environment on the part of each of its inhabitants.

It can also be noted that there is some internal inconsistency in the ecological culture of students, which consists in distancing ecological knowledge, their value fixing in the mind, and the actual ecological behavior. Moreover, the magnitude of the distance between these levels of ecological culture to a certain extent depends on the belonging of young people to a certain socio-professional group. In conclusion, it should be noted that at the present stage of development of society, the ecological situation indicates the need to strengthen the spiritual and moral culture as an integral part of the ecological culture of youth and society as a whole. The criterion for the formation of an ecological culture is actions, behavior and activities of a person that are justified from the point of view of the laws of ecology,

actions that are ecologically consistent with the socio-natural environment. In other words, professional activity and behavior must "adjust" to natural processes and be carried out within the framework of environmental and moral imperatives permitted. There is no purely technical or technological solution to the issues of overcoming possible crises. No matter how important saving technologies, water, air, soil purification systems, nature conservation systems are, they are not able to improve the situation. Proceeding from this, in the formation of ecological culture, the key role belongs to social institutions: the state, the family, the education system, the media, the result of the upbringing of which will be a harmoniously developed and culturally developed (in the broadest sense of the word) personality. In general, the formation of an ecological culture is a completely solvable task. Ecological movements and organizations could play a big role here.

References:

1. Beck U. Risk society: towards a new modernity. Translated by M. Ritter. London: Sage, 1992. 260 p.
2. Giddens A. Runaway world: how globalization is reshaping our lives. London: Profile, 1999. XIII, 104 p.
3. Dezhnikova N.S. Ecological education in the context of socio-cultural dynamics / N.S. Dezhnikova // Pedagogy. - 2002. - No. 10. - P.51-56.
4. Kim L. A. Ecological movement as a factor in the development of civil society in Uzbekistan // Sociological science and social practice. 2020. V. 8. No. 1. S. 150–166. DOI: 10.19181/snsp.2020.8.1.7101
5. Kraeva N.V., Makarova V.I. Man and the environment: natural science and humanitarian aspects // Human Ecology. 2014. No. 1. S. 27-35
6. Mid M. Culture and the world of childhood. M.: Nauka, 1988. 429 p.
7. Murdoch J.P. Common denominator of cultures: Per. from English. // Culturology: Digest. RAN INION. 2005
8. Self-regulation in the youth environment: typology and modeling: monograph / Yu. A. Zubok, O. A. Aleksandrova, M. B. Bulanova [and others]; under total ed. Yu. A. Zubok; FNISC RAS. - Belgorod: "Epicenter", 2022. - 360 p.

9. "On measures to implement the National goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development for the period up to 2030" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of October 20, 2018 No. 841

10. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept of environmental protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" dated October 30, 2019 No. UP-5863